

Towards a sustainable agri-food ecosystem: the case study of South Korean public food procurement

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Abstract

Purpose: Public food procurement (PFP) plays an important role in establishing such agri-food systems. Our study explores local food system stakeholders' response to PFP interventions by addressing the question of how PFP transforms agri-food systems and how this new agri-food ecosystem is governed.

Design/methodology/approach: This article presents and discusses a unique case study of Jeonbuk, a rural province in South Korea, which successfully transformed its agri-food system into an ecosystem through its sustainability-oriented innovations (SOI) among born ecopreneur farmers. This case not only offers insights into a novel way to create value chains through legislative, executive, and judicial governance but also extends the body of knowledge on agri-food systems by introducing the concept of an agri-food ecosystem.

Findings and Originality: Our findings indicate the importance of the ecosystem governance and knowledge exchange among internal and external ecosystem stakeholders. In particular, PFP institutions play a crucial role in facilitating the operation of public meal centers and cooperation among actors. The study further extends the agricultural cooperatives research and contributes to a better understanding of the role of a municipality and an agri-food intermediary in the governance process involving producers and kitchens.

Practical Implications: Taking an ecosystem lens to agri-food systems may offer them a wider perspective and better understanding of the governance structures necessary to successfully execute public interventions. Lastly, the Korean case differs from other developing countries, but its role model qualities could help to implement successful school meal programs elsewhere.

Keywords: Public food procurement, public meal center, school meal, agri-food ecosystem, ecosystem governance, agricultural cooperatives

1. Introduction

In the last two decades, international development agencies and national governments have implemented food programs aimed at sustaining and developing public agri-food systems (FAO, 2019, Ruane, 2019). Despite the evolution of food safety, quality standards, and sustainable business models as part of the private agri-food systems (Henson and Reardon, 2005), the public agri-food systems continue to impact the supply chains by supporting a combination of activities and institutions for agricultural and food production and consumption. School nutrition programs are one such public support program, which is typically federally assisted meal programs, often operating in public or both public and nonprofit private schools along with residential childcare institutions. Such programs provide nutritionally balanced meals at little or no cost to children while ensuring high-quality food delivery, which significantly influences the healthy diet of the citizens as well as the local economy (Otsuki, 2014). In addition to impacting agricultural production and the local environment, such initiatives also constitute an important element in a global agenda. According to the United Nations, these programs contribute to public food procurement (PFP), which covers activities aimed at achieving Sustainable Development Goals such as hunger reduction and education improvement (WFP, 2017).

While most of the studies investigating PFP focus on procurement standards and the improvement of diets or cooking practices, less attention has been given to the governance of PFP and its linkage to agri-food production systems and agricultural cooperatives. In reality, public sector food programs become an expanding market channel for small-scale, local farms (Feenstra and Hardesty, 2016) and born-ecopreneur farmers (henceforth simply “farmers”), connecting actors and activities among farms in rural areas to large urban areas. We define ecopreneur farmers as farmers who engage in agriculture in a way that protects the environment, encourages sustainability, and generates social value (Sarkar and Pansera, 2017, Schaper,

2016). The emergence of new market channels along with increasing demand for sustainability-oriented innovations (SOIs) encompassing institutional and social change calls for a new approach to better understand traditional agricultural cooperatives (Lee et al., 2020, Ma et al., 2023, Ma et al., 2022) and agri-food systems in PFPs (Adams et al., 2016), which could be offered by ecosystem thinking. In this context, the ecosystem approach builds on the combination of innovation and agri-food system approach, extending it by providing much more dynamic and long-term thinking centered on complementary competencies and assets and joined value proposition (Jacobides et al., 2018, Rong et al., 2020, Scaringella and Radziwon, 2018) largely embedded in the regional context (Radziwon, 2023). Inspired by Bizikova et al. (2020) and (Cobben et al., 2022), we define an agri-food ecosystem as *the collaborative arrangements through which farmers [ecopreneurs] combine their individual [often small-scale] offerings into a coherent, society-facing (both rural and urban) solution*. Instead of focusing on a technology platform, which is often at the center of a regional innovation ecosystem, we focus on the PFP, which serves as a platform for exchanging knowledge and goods (Cobben et al., 2022, Rong et al., 2020). As the demand for high-quality food in urban areas is steadily increasing, there is a need to better understand and further develop a sustainable agri-food ecosystem by uniting all of the involved actors. Given the potential space wherein PFP aims to source from local contract farming or direct purchase, the local agricultural authorities could design and implement public policy interventions in a manner that will largely contribute to the development of rural agri-food ecosystems.

The knowledge gap that we are addressing lies at the intersection of the rapidly expanding market channel for small-scale, local farms (Feenstra and Hardesty, 2016) and institutional environments surrounding the public agri-food system. Informed by the research stream of agri-food systems, agricultural cooperatives, and innovation ecosystems, our primary focus is on the governance and orchestration of the agri-food ecosystem (Nambisan and

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Sawhney, 2011, Dhanaraj and Parkhe, 2006, Wareham et al., 2014). This article thus aims to explore the PFP governance of institutions in the value chain governance by focusing on the case of South Korean public meal centers in Jeonbuk Province, which play the role of agri-food ecosystem orchestrator. We chose the unique case of PFP in South Korea (Siggelkow, 2007), because it is an example of a successful, running collaboration between rural and urban agri-food ecosystems that emerged in the context of a series of PFP interventions. The Korean public meal center concept is exceptional, there are abundant cases of Food Hub Organizations (FHO) in the US and food governance in European civil society. That is why we focus on the public meal centers (aka. school meal support centers), which first started in rural regions, then spread to municipalities in urban-rural mixed areas, and urban districts gradually developed their own public meal centers in their administrative territories, which have become an important ecosystem orchestrator. Our research addresses the following research questions: How does Public Food Procurement transform local agri-food systems? And how is this new agri-food ecosystem governed?

Informed by research in agricultural cooperatives and farmer organizations (Lee et al., 2020, Ma et al., 2022, Bizikova et al., 2020) we investigate our case through an ecosystem lens, where ecosystem actors (predominantly small-scale, local farmers) offer their supply of local agri-food to public food kitchens. Acting as a collective, the latter can develop a superior value proposition to that which each would be able to offer alone. Under these notions of conceptualization, the study identifies which institutions are created and, conversely, how institutions affect the relations between actors to shed light on the quality aspects of local agri-food procurement.

Our research contributes to the PFP literature by offering insights into how intermediary actors, such as public kitchens (here, agri-food ecosystem orchestrator), handle interventions aimed at developing sustainability-oriented innovations aimed at promoting new, sustainable

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eating habits (Goggins, 2018). Moreover, inspired by agricultural collaboratives (Lee et al., 2020, Ma et al., 2022, Bizikova et al., 2020) and ecosystem thinking (Radziwon and Bogers, 2019, Jacobides et al., 2018, Adner, 2017), we try to transfer lessons learned from small, technology-oriented firms to ecopreneur farmers, who operate in a more legislation-driven environment. Last but not least, we contribute to sustainability-oriented innovation (SOI) by examining farmers, considered here as born ecopreneurs, who collectively arrange and combine their individual offerings [produce and delivery] to address society-oriented solutions (Hansen and Grosse-Dunker, 2012).

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. The article begins by reviewing the value chain governance framework with a focus on the role of institutions. We then elaborate on the analytical strategy of data collection and analysis methods. Section 4 focuses on the general case background information related to the condition of the local agri-food policy of Jeonbuk Province and school meals in Korea. Afterward, we discuss the findings and offer practical recommendations, both to agri-food ecosystem orchestrators and policymakers.

2. Theoretical frameworks

2.1. Value chains in agri-food systems

Numerous studies of agri-food systems have analyzed the value chain concept. Kaplinsky (2004) defines a value chain as “*the full range of activities that are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the intermediary phase of production, delivery to final consumers.*” Value chain analysis allows the mapping out of specific fields of production and the development of relevant policies to facilitate the participation of small farms in the market (Rich et al., 2011). Agri-food systems are closely intertwined with the agricultural production fields, but they also consist of multi-layered structures with institutional interventions, technical development, and practices across the agri-food value chain, which

largely resemble low- and mid-tech SME ecosystems (small- and medium-sized enterprises) (Capone et al., 2014, Radziwon and Bogers, 2019, Radziwon and Bogers, 2018). Similar to a business or innovation ecosystem, an agri-food ecosystem has a relatively large number of stakeholders; here, small-scale, local farmers, contribute products to the ecosystem's joint value proposition.

Our study examines the agri-food systems through a structural view of ecosystems proposed by Adner (2017). According to the structural view, an ecosystem is defined as the alignment of partners – farmers, a municipality, and public meal kitchens aligned by an orchestrator; here, a public meal center towards a joint value. The value chain notion can promote local food ecosystems that yield joint values in the entire system, from farmers to customers (Stevenson and Pirog, 2008). In this way, the joint contributions of diverse local food farmers as a collective are much more competitive than any single one could ever be. In this context the agri-food ecosystem covers a wider range of actors than farming organizations or agricultural cooperatives, which could also be part of the ecosystems providing educational training, access to newest research and access to technology (Wossen et al., 2017, Bizikova et al., 2020, Ma et al., 2022).

SOI traditionally involves “*making intentional changes to an organization's philosophy and values, as well as to its products, processes or practices to serve the specific purpose of creating and realizing social and environmental value in addition to economic returns*” (Adams et al., 2016). SOI has typically been discussed in the context of firms and organizations transforming agri-food systems, which is why best practice governance procedures regarding innovation-oriented farmers forming public school kitchens provide a thought-provoking research setup (Siggelkow, 2007). In the public agri-food system, the farmers serve as born ecopreneurs, which, alongside SMEs, are central contributors to sustainable development (Klewitz and Hansen, 2014, Hansen and Grosse-Dunker, 2012). As much as SMEs may resist,

react, and anticipate some of the SOIs, farmers are much better positioned to embrace SOI through their agri-food system value chains. Such SOI-oriented value chains offer an important, innovation-stimulated transformation point, where PFP institutions contribute to the emergence of the agri-food ecosystem. All the collaborative arrangements aimed at building agri-food ecosystems strive to unite a large number of small-scale farmers, who, if well organized, can deliver complementary food supplies that constitute the joint value proposition. Both the complementarity and interdependence of farmers fulfill the ecosystem membership criteria (Adner, 2017, Jacobides et al., 2018). These activities must all be aligned by an orchestrator. In such a complicated system, the role of ecosystem orchestration overlaps with value chain governance, which offers an additional challenge regarding the multilayer structure of collaborative relationships with multiple stakeholder involvement. The ecosystem perspective (Adner, 2017, Jacobides et al., 2018) focuses on the orchestrator tasks related to the materialization of the joint value proposition, compatibility of incentives, and motives and information exchange among partners (Brem and Radziwon, 2017, Scaringella and Radziwon, 2018). While agricultural cooperatives literature offers valuable insights into both beneficial services offered by farmer organizations that allow better access to the market, higher crops yield and reducing the risk exposure (Ma et al., 2022, Bizikova et al., 2020, Lin et al., 2022). Combining both literature streams helps us in uncovering a broader range of interactions between all actors involved in public food procurement oriented towards sustainable innovation, economic growth and social development.

The conceptualization of governance plays a pivotal role in developing and investigating the analytical approach of the value chain, along with the systemic element: comprehensive integration for efficiency (Kaplinsky, 2004, Kaplinsky and Morris, 2000). Value chain governance focuses on different types of coordination together with results delivered through the allocation of resources and rents, including the management of quality

standards and their enforcement (Ponte and Gibbon, 2005). To manage product quality, which is one of the crucial elements in value chain governance, global supermarket chains have invested considerable effort in institutionalizing product quality requirements and the communication thereof (Ponte and Gibbon, 2005).

Meanwhile, the emerging changes in quality and process standards-based demand on agri-food from sophisticated consumers and sustainable social, economic, and environmental policy goals impact the coordination in the value chain. Responding to these changes on the consumption side, the systems controlling the quality and monitoring compliance become imperative in the management of the chain (Ponte and Gibbon, 2005, Dolan and Humphrey, 2000). As the fragmentation of production has accrued spatially and functionally, coordination between actors becomes an essential issue in the value chain. Gereffi et al. (2005) have argued that “more customized service or product” and greater partnerships may bring out additional transaction costs, which provides an inducement for the leading firm to internalize certain production processes and to introduce a variety of protective measures. The relations between firms vary from “outsourcing” to “in-house,” depending on how far the leading entity holds the controlling ownership over the production process (Altenburg, 2006, Gereffi et al., 2005).

2.2 PFP institutions and actors

PFP is comprehensively influenced by a wide range of institutions (Morgan and Sonnino, 2007). Throughout this paper, we refer to institutions not only in terms of formal rules, but also as informal constraints as well as norms, precedents, and organizational factors that to a large extent structure political behavior (Hall, 1997, North, 1994). From the view of market relations, institutions ensure trust and certainty between economic actors by coordinating networks through information sharing, monitoring actors’ processes and results, and sanctions and incentives (Hall and Soskice, 2001, Ostrom, 1990). These institutional elements can encourage

certain activities or behaviors among actors by providing guidelines and imposing restrictions (Scott, 2013), which consist of “the rules of the game” in society that present as laws, regulations, norms, and rules (North, 1994). Various PFP institutions are closely intertwined with the public procurement process and catering characteristics. Apart from the purchase of household or private catering, PFP is constrained by the legal structure and is required to comply with competitive bidding system processes.

Food regulations and practices are important institutions for participation in the PFP value chain. While North (1990) stressed the extrinsic and enforced feature of institutions that regulates actor behavior through rules by third parties, scholars pay progressive attention to how actors interact as rule-makers with institutions, mutually and reflexively, which constructs “new” rules based on the existing social norms (Jackson, 2010, Hodgson, 2006). In particular, quality standards are socially arranged institutions that can change the producer and consumer practices through value chains (Wijk et al., 2010), and quality standards establish barriers to newcomers or suppliers to value chains in developing countries (Ponte and Gibbon, 2005). Mercado et al. (2018) noted how the food safety regulatory standards hinder small-scale farmer participation in value chains because such frameworks favor large-scale farmers targeting the global market. In the case study in Bolivia, highly food-safety-concerned municipalities adopted alternative verifying measures to enable local farmers to supply school meals (Mercado et al., 2018). Following similar hesitancy due to food safety regulations, school caterers in the Berlin region require the delivery of pre-processed vegetables, which may act as a barrier to local organic farmers (Braun et al., 2018). The high level of food hygiene standards, which requires investment, may hinder the progress of developing sustainability-oriented innovation via small-sized initiatives (Van Gameren et al., 2015). To address the challenges facing local farms, including barriers to logistics, distribution, operations, and urban regulations (Matacena, 2016, Mount, 2012), the orchestrator role must be better understood,

both on the ecosystem side as well as value chain governance and collaboration with PFP institutions.

With regards to the regulations and criteria surrounding PFP above, we also paid attention to the role of the public authorities, which establish and execute several PFP rules. PFP regulations from the municipal to national levels may be applied to the multi-layered aspects of the purchase, from food selection to logistics, which is complicated (Conner et al., 2012). Governments can play a crucial role by helping stakeholders to recognize opportunities and enter into the chain, supporting proactive policy measures (Kaplinsky, 2004). In the study of cases in Denmark, Italy, Finland, and Norway, Nölting (2009) underlines the role of government with institutional support, ranging from legislation to financial support, which has effectively increased organic food consumption in Danish schools. While one of the dominant topics of PFP is the food supply chain that challenges and benefits producers and caterers as a management issue (Stefani et al., 2017), there is little discussion of the roles played by public authorities in the PFP value chains. Studies emphasize the important role played by regional municipalities in designing and implementing agri-food initiatives (Renting and Wiskerke, 2010), but we still know very little about the coordination links of PFP across different levels of a local institution, municipality, or government (Otsuki, 2014). In the comparative case study of Korean school meal support centers, municipalities that have operated the meal centers denoted a significant level of satisfaction with the procurement process and food quality (Lee et al., 2020, Chung, 2021, Lim and Yang, 2013). Gaddis and Jeon (2022) identify the notion of “precautionary infrastructure” to explain new supply systems to ensure a stable channel for sustainable farms. This study demonstrates how universal free school meal programs in South Korea subsidized by governments can create niche markets to encourage sustainable agrifood systems.

Due to the complexity of institutional PFP environments, the governance structure plays an important role in determining the scope of knowledge interaction between all food suppliers. Massa and Testa (2009), in a comparative case study of small Italian food producers, argued that food firms were likely to adopt different processes for managing knowledge, depending on which purpose they pursue to deal with knowledge. This highlights the importance of institutional norms that have a significant influence on the participation and communication of actors in the PFP chain from the perspective of value chain governance.

3. Methods

This article presents and discusses a unique case study (Siggelkow, 2007): Jeonbuk, a rural province in South Korea, which successfully transformed its agri-food system into an ecosystem via sustainability-oriented innovations among born ecopreneur farmers. The transformation of the agri-food system to the ecosystem through farmers' orchestration of the collectively established meal centers is not the most intuitive policy scenario. In this context, the orchestrating role shifts from the local governments to intermediary actors which handle large volumes of food and become a focal point for interventions aimed at developing SOI in the agri-food sector. SOI has typically been discussed in the context of firms and organizations transforming agri-food systems, which is why best practice governance procedures regarding innovation-oriented farmers successfully forming public school kitchens provide a thought-provoking research setup (Siggelkow, 2007).

The research project employed a multimethod approach, combining a case study, interviews, document analysis, and participant observation. Applying multiple research methods enables case studies not only to broaden the researcher's perspective on an issue but also to improve the convergence of evidence (Yin, 2017). Simons (2009) noted how a case study is considered a frame aggregation of research design that may embrace several methods rather than a method itself.

The data collection methods involved both formal and informal interviews. First, semi-structured interviews were conducted, which commonly comprise one of the essential elements of case study research (Yin, 2017). We identified eight key informant interviews in Jeonbuk and prepared a set of interview guides for three interviewee groups: governments, public meal centers, and schools. From the government side, the current team manager or a government representative from various levels of government was selected for the interview (see **Table 1**). Representativeness and sufficient field experience are our criteria for the selection of interviewees. To better understand the farmer's perspective, heads of public meal centers who were both farmers and involved in establishing the center from the beginning were invited, because most of these centers are run by agriculture organizations. Dietitians with more than 10 years of field experience in designing a daily diet and procuring food for schools were interviewed and formed a focus group. The interview and observation process was conducted from December 2018 to February 2019, and the relevant documents had been collected by May 2019.

Table 1. The list of interviewees (Source: Authors work)

	Identifier	Description
G1	National government	A government employee in charge of the food plan strategy
G2	Provincial government	Local food team manager of Jeonbuk Provincial Government
G3	Municipality	Local food team manager of Gunsan County
G4	Municipality	Local food team manager of Wanju County
P1	Producer	Head of public meal center of Gunsan, farmer
P2	Producer	Head of public meal center of Wanju, distribution manager
D1	Dietitian	Gunsan (+10 years of experience in Jeonbuk)
D2	Dietitian	Wanju (+10 years of experience in Jeonbuk)
D3	Dietitian	Wanju (+10 years of experience in Jeonbuk)

The interviewees were asked about the process of establishing PFP, the related institutional changes, how to encourage actor participation in such PFP, and the use of local food in school kitchens, focusing on which kinds of institutions governed the procurement and production practices. As we were not allowed to record the interviews with the dietitians, notes were taken to capture the main points from this interview (Bhattacharya, 2017). These three unrecorded interviews were conducted in January 2019. To achieve a more open conversation, we began by asking about their experiences and perceptions of local food school meals in the period 2014–18, and first thereafter proceeded to more sensitive information regarding the evaluation of the actual food procurement process and the hands-on changes and PFP intervention.

Considering the sensitive nature of the study concerning the analysis and critical evaluation of the PFP interventions, we complemented our interviews with observations and document analysis, the latter involving the systematic evaluation of offline and online documents (Bowen, 2009), which ranged from administrative documents to informal memoranda (Yin, 2017). Our document selection prioritized the officially published guidelines and municipal ordinance, including the school meal guideline released by the Jeonbuk Province Educational Office and the local food strategy published by the Jeonbuk Provincial Government (see Appendix A). Collected documents from municipalities were evaluated using the eight-step process suggested by O'Leary (2017): from gathering relevant texts through assessing the authenticity of the documents and exploring agenda biases to asking questions and exploring documents' contents. Following these steps, we conduct the analysis focusing more on the authorities and institutional mechanism rather than quantifying the frequent use of certain words or concepts. In addition to the main data collection from interviews and documents, participant observation was made in the relevant workshop. The workshop was held by the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs of Korea, 19–20 December 2018

at Choongnam Province to share model cases for Food Planning in the regions. The scope of observation ranged from formal speeches and presentations to informal networking meetings.

Our observations also encompass the analysis in which stakeholders are involved and how regulations or public policies influence their roles in the chain. Analyzing the governance of the value chain enabled us to identify the major stakeholders and to better understand how policies influence them in the value chain (Kaplinsky, 2004). To analyze value chain governance, we consider the three types of governance – legislative, executive, and judicial governance – like the separation of powers in a democratic government. To specify, there are fundamental conditions to taking part in the chain (legislative governance); and based on complying with those legislative standards, it is likely to support potential or existing participants proactively to meet the consented principles (executive governance); audit systems are also required to control compliance with the existing rules and procedures (judicial governance) (Kaplinsky, 2004).

The study took the phased approach to categorize and code the data. Transcriptions translated from Korean to English were analyzed, relying on the theoretical frameworks organizing the case study (Yin, 2017). Firstly, any types of formal or informal rules and practices that may affect food sourcing were embraced. Text from each source was coded into two primary groups: objective–normative clauses and socio-emotional expression. In the next step, these data were re-coded according to function: challenges, food selection (production), and communication. These codes were disaggregated into three categories: legislative, executive, and judicial governance, as discussed in the previous paragraph. Another point of the analysis is the change of its adoption, with developing descriptive interpretation (Yin, 2017, Yin, 2015). Based on the value chain governance matrix, we made a descriptive comparison of the situations before and after the regional government launch of the PFP initiatives in 2015. These analytical processes led the authors to find the gap between the knowledge and

expectations of the different groups and to examine which elements affect actors' behaviors and decisions regarding PFP.

4. Jeonbuk Province PFP – background

4.1. Local food and PFP policies

The Jeonbuk case was chosen because of the province's success with local food and school meal policies after introducing the novel concept of the farmers' market and the public meal center for the first time in South Korea. Jeonbuk is one of 17 South Korean provinces and consists of 14 municipalities. The main crop is rice, which accounts for 65% of the arable land in the province with large-sized farms, 53% in the national average, while horticulture production is relatively low, meaning that this region is generally not suitable for sourcing local PFP, which requires greater food diversity.

Meanwhile, Wanju, one of the rural municipalities in Jeonbuk, initiated its local food project as a rural community development policy. Provincial Government and Wanju organized small farm cooperatives based on capacity development and came up with farmers' supermarkets, where consumers buy locally grown fresh agriproducts. After the Wanju local food success story, Provincial Government provided financial and institutional support to expand the systems to other municipalities. Consequently, the Jeonbuk local food policy has become a model case of a direct sales channel for agri-food products and rural development in Korea, recording an annual turnover of €72 million in 2018 at 36 local food markets.

Based on this local food policy success, the Jeonbuk provincial government has launched its school meal program, which accounts for a large part of PFP. Jeonbuk has approximately 240,000 pupils in 770 schools. As of 2019, the Jeonbuk budget includes free lunches for all pupils.

As regards the agricultural production systems, the provincial government has supported the establishment of a “School Meal Support Center” in each municipality supplying locally grown organic rice and vegetables to schools, and 13 such centers have been established in 14 municipalities, the second-highest ratio among the Korean provinces. These centers have different organizational characteristics. They are operated by either a municipality (Wanju, Jeonju), local organic farmer cooperatives (i.e., Gunsan, Jangsu), or national agricultural organizations (other provinces).

4.2.South Korean school meal policies

Most South Korean schoolchildren are provided with a lunch from the school canteen, and its supportive policies remain at the discretion of the public sector. In 2013, all Korean schools provided meals (Woo, 2015), which is a significant increase compared to 1997, when only 58% of schools and 39% of pupils received meals. The estimated annual cost of the Korean school meal programs is approximately €4.7 billion. Every school has a kitchen managed by a qualified dietitian, except for a few rural, extremely small schools where the kitchens are managed collectively by one dietitian.

Most of the school meals are completely free of charge for pupils and their parents due to generous municipal subsidies. Since the municipal election in 2010, civil society has consistently pushed the authorities to prioritize the political agenda of free, organic school meals in the election. This agenda has become an important and politically sensitive issue for candidates throughout Korea. Consequently, 82.5% of all pupils fully benefit from the free school lunch program in 2018.

The administrative support systems for the Korean school meal programs are multi-layered and complex. The primary responsibility for school meals is borne by the educational authorities, the Ministry of Education (national level), and the municipal Education Offices. The public administrations of local autonomous provinces of Korea consist of two entities, the

Provincial Government and Education Office, and the Education Office bears the main responsibility for the school meal program. As regards the budget, three public authorities – provincial government, municipality, and Education Office – provide the financial resources to execute the school meal programs, as there are no national rules for budget contributions to these programs among these entities; the ratio of burden varied by region (See Figure 1).

As regards the bidding systems, schools in several provinces must utilize “eaT,” the online tendering system operated by the national agri-food agency. This system is based on the lowest-costing bids. Even though the relevant laws allow free contracts for small-sum purchases with certain conditions, school canteens generally do not take the risk of signing outside of bid-free contracts, as this is considered out of their general practices.

Figure 1. The government structure of Jeonbuk school meal programs (Source: Authors work)

5. Findings

5.1. Creating PFP value chains – the role of legislative governance

We first examined the creation of PFP value chains through legislative governance, here concerning the school canteen's food selection standards in practice and how stakeholders joined and changed institutions. Initially, our findings indicated that school kitchens are primarily governed by the comprehensive Jeonbuk Province Education Office guideline, which serves as a legislative document: "the School Meal Guideline." This annually revised school meal guideline consists of the general terms of compliance with food catering, ranging from food safety and quality to the procurement process, which is compatible with the relevant national regulations. The establishment of the guideline is stipulated in the national law (The School Meals Act). Annually, Education Office produces a draft guideline and conducts the-consultation hearing periodically for the municipalities during the preceding year. Aside from a few minor hygiene- and budget-related parts, most of the guideline remains unchanged every year.

The notable change in this practice is that Provincial Government tried to intervene in the formulation of the Education Office guidelines. Despite regular consultation and hearing procedures in Jeonbuk Province, no municipality in Jeonbuk, including the PG, had advanced an official opinion related to food selection or procurement before 2014. Since 2014, two notable alterations were carried out. First, Provincial Government and Wanju sought to revise the procurement part of the guideline to initiate a pilot project in 2015 favoring locally sourced food procurement for schools. After months of lengthy negotiations, finally, the stakeholders reached an agreement on a memorandum of understanding between the Education Office and Wanju, herein Education Office accepted its conditional application. Wanju then launched its pilot school meal project related to local food procurement. As a result, on the condition that both Provincial Government and Education Office agreed, it opened the door for the Jeonbuk public meal centers to be allowed to source local foods for schools via direct contracting.

Figure 2. School meal procurement before the public meal center launched (Source: Authors work)

Second, the provision of the use of locally processed food products was adopted in the guideline. Previously, as there were no explicit regulations for procuring processed products from small local farming enterprises, dietitians were reluctant to order them for public catering, preferring products manufactured by large companies with institutional standards. D1 stated that

We believe tofu or soy sauce from our neighbors is made with good ingredients, but their products aren't usually certified. We knew that tofu or soy sauce from big companies may contain imported GMO beans, but at least they have official labels, like HACCP¹. D1 Gunsan Dietitian

¹ HACCP stands for Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points. It is a preventive approach to food safety, typically focusing on biological, chemical, physical hazards.

During 2016 and 2017, Provincial Government came up with its own standard for processed food made from locally grown crops, vegetables, and fruits. To implement this standard, Jeonbuk had a couple of non-official meetings with the Education Office, after which they lightened the administrative burden and gave the canteens incentives to use locally proceed food, such as tofu, soy sauce, and red pepper powder.

A couple of clauses in the municipal ordinance have been amended or enacted in 2015 in favor of procuring locally grown food (See **Table 2**). To explain the definition and establishment of the committee for the center, Provincial Government initially inserted supportive clauses to activate the roles of the public centers in the region and school meals. These included an additional function of the center regarding local food diet education. Secondly, it introduced the concept of the planned cultivation of local products matching with total expected consumption. Scholars of the local food initiatives highlighted the advantages of a school meal program that could be directly linked to annual menu plans requiring very concrete and large food volumes to be supplied in a particular period (Commission, 2011, Goggins, 2018). This implies that local food supplies to schools must comply with the agreed standards and procedures.

In particular, the enactment of the clause in 2015 opened its integrated support plan for local food and school meals. The Jeonbuk Governor had to establish the school meal support plan in connection with the local food plan, which followed the “Local food support ordinance of Jeonbuk Province.” Consequently, two separate policy plans for local food and school meal support have developed into its first triennium local food scheme in 2017, which suggests the range of its future financial investment in public meals.

Table 2. Changes to the Jeonbuk provincial school meal ordinance (Source: Author, based upon data taken from Jeonbuk provincial ordinance of school meal 2011 and 2015)

Amendment	Ordinance of school meal 2011	Ordinance of school meal 2015
Definition of the public meal center	an operational system, where the municipality manages proper production, logistics, and supply control functions of school food materials	an operational system, where the municipality manages the proper function of production, logistics, supply control of food materials for school, and local food diet education
Enactment	Ordinance of school meal 2015	
Planned production	When it comes to supporting school meal by-products directly, the municipality supplies agri-products according to the annual cultivation plan concerning the total quantity of needs from consumers, the proper standards, and discussion among producers through the center.	
Committee	The governor shall establish a committee for the center and report its minutes to a deliberation committee for the support of the school meal service to expand the public role of the center in society under the jurisdiction of the committee.	
Establishment of plan	The Jeonbuk Governor should establish the school meal support plan in connection with the local food plan, which established the following “Local food support ordinance of Jeonbuk Province.”	

As regards public administration, Provincial Government and municipalities feature an array of integrated policies in school meal support. This adjustment affected the role of the public meal center. School meal programs had traditionally fallen under the purview of municipal education or interior authorities. Previously, a municipality only conducted the administrative part of budget execution for school meal programs in compliance with a given legislative procedure. In Jeonbuk, the education department was responsible for the two relevant programs: free school meals and organic school meals. Only school meal support for organic rice use was fulfilled under the Agriculture Bureau. By reorganizing the internal process, the two former programs have been transferred to the Agriculture Bureau, meaning that all Provincial Government school meal programs have been controlled by a single agricultural administration. The local food team, which was newly established by the Agriculture Bureau in 2014, assumed responsibility for school meal support, organic vegetable programs, and organic rice school

meals. The team has issued the official policy recommendation to other Jeonbuk municipalities about how it would be highly desirable to make the integrated team for school meal programs.

5.2. Creating PFP value chains – the role of executive governance

In terms of the executive role in the value chain, each agri-food ecosystem member, along with the involved institutions, expressed significant interest in the SOI initiatives. The dietitians' experiences indicated that communication with suppliers was important for local food procurement. The channels of communication were grouped into two parts: official bidding and daily claims. Before the public meal center was launched and took the ecosystem orchestration role, the relationships between schools and distributors were rather fragmented (See **Figure 2**). Formal, informative channels between kitchens and suppliers ran via the monthly electronic bids run by the public state agency, eaT. Like other public bidding systems, the eaT institutional procedure required the verification of a supplier's qualifications and performance, as documented by objective certifications. In turn, its proposal was assessed by quantity, low-price-based criteria. As winning a bid and signing a contract depend on the standardized, digitalized system for the short-term contract, a school dietitian had limited discretion. Jeonbuk school canteens make a monthly contract for procurement, while other PFPs may make longer-term, season-long agreements (3 months) or annual agreements. In the interviews, the dietitians complained that there were few elements with which to judge the value of locally grown food. Even though several kitchens required distributors to guarantee the quality of raw materials, it was hard to force them to do so, because their relations with private distributors were considered temporary. Under such circumstances, dietitians stated that it was difficult to bring up complaints regarding food quality or requirements of local food because the only feedback between suppliers and procurers took place while discussing the quantity-based estimates and order sheets based on items and prices. D2 mentioned that

The bidding contract is only computer work with numbers. And they were changed a lot because the only standard to decide the bid winner was low price.

So they didn't need to take care of food quality. **D2 Wanju Dietitian**

Only serious hygiene or food safety accidents could be considered as reasons for imposing legal sanctions on the involved distributors.

Dietitians pointed out that one of the crucial capabilities of suppliers is to deal with momentary demands in everyday catering. Apart from the official and electronic bidding systems, in reality, dietitians were frequently in touch with distributors after signing the contract. Canteens check the quantity and quality of the agri-food product delivery early each morning. If the delivered products diverge from the order in quality, quantity, or substance, a dietitian must file a complaint, and distributors are supposed to rectify the situation before 11 am. However, dietitians and producers all agreed that the canteen requirements varied, depending on their catering environments and the subjective criteria of the manager, which were not described in the tendering offer.

Placing the orchestrator function in the public meal center contributed to improving communication practices through committee activities and long-term relations. By activating working-level meetings, canteens have a chance to influence production practices. Under the National School Meal Act, Education Office shall establish a school meal services committee, and Provincial Government may run another deliberation committee on support. In the case study of school meal services in Pisa, Italy, the Canteen Committee played a crucial communicative role in engaging public authorities with stakeholders through the co-production process (Galli et al., 2014). However, these two existing committees in Jeonbuk took charge of the policy-level agenda. The main purpose of the school meal support committee, which was held once or twice annually, was to decide broad program strategies and its overall budget,

which was not fit to discuss practical, detailed requirements from every kitchen. As most of the committee members are not experts in catering or production in the field, official communications might be isolated from everyday reality.

Meanwhile, according to the municipal ordinance, the new public meal center committee has organized and subsequently conducted its activities every month since the launch of the center. This committee consists of working-level members: the head of the meal center, the municipal manager, and school dietitian representatives. The main purpose of this monthly meeting is to decide the prices, terms, and items of products for the next month's menu. Participants at such meetings can discuss the quality of local food and to understand seasonal conditions of agricultural products and their prices in advance, which may adjust the kitchen menus, as well as production and processing procedures, including supply quantity and packaging from farmers.

The public meal center as an ecosystem orchestrator provides dietitians with another space to be involved in the response and feedback process, which the official bidding hardly deals with. Setting up the substantive operations of the center and its committee enabled knowledge sharing, which influences the mutual expectations of farmers and kitchens. Through the novel concept of food governance with the center, new daily coordination between schools and producers was established. Dietitians considered this relation as a reliable and collective channel to suppliers. Compared to the low capability of the previous private distributors, kitchens expressed relatively high satisfaction with the performance of the public center due to its comprehensive response. They expressed trust in the public center commissioned by the municipality or run by farmers' organizations.

The institutional attempts by the public meal center to improve knowledge sharing and service quality appeared to enhance the farmers' capacity and participation in the food

ecosystem activities. The participation and capacity building of local farms for PFP pivots around the roles of the meal center as controlled by the municipality. Before establishing the center, local farms had no touchpoint with schools; there were wholesale or middle dealers between them (See **Figure 2**). One of the prerequisite conditions of the establishment of the Jeonbuk center was to ensure farmer participation. Aligned with municipal policies, the Wanju and Gunsan centers carried out functions that assist and guide farmers to produce suitable vegetables that meet kitchen standards and expectations, such as product size and quality.

Apart from the technical needs, one of the challenges facing the individual local farms regarding catering services is the lack of capacity to supply diverse items year-round, which may be associated with uncertain sales and seasonal variability. Sales uncertainty hinders the participation of local farms in the PFP market and with respect to adopting new varieties. This could be a great way to motivate farmers to maintain sustainable cultivation systems, like organic farming, and to signal to them to draw up annual farming plans, which reduce their financial uncertainty and risk (Darly, 2012). The meal center organized the demand from schools, allocating them to local farms with specific amounts of supply (See **Figure 3**). Along with this local data, the center designed an overall, year-round production plan. To complement the capacity inadequacies of the local farms, the center implemented a couple of technical support and financial incentives on behalf of the municipality. In correspondence with incentive institutions, a public meal center has the actual authority and internal criteria to impose penalties on farmers who violate the production rules, such as pesticide overuse. This is a very important role contributing to the public meal center serving as an agri-food ecosystem orchestrator.

Meanwhile, the authors also found a couple of negative responses to local food PFP. From the consumer perspective, one of the school's greatest concerns was rising food prices from the regions and the replacement of defective and/or low-quality products. Compared to

industrial, market-based products, public meal centers secure the limited capacity to obtain enough items and quantities of food every day. The dietitians were also worried about the quality gap between different regions; for example, they knew that the Gunsan and Wanju centers and farmers perform better on services and supply than other counties. As the dietitians rotate regionally within the province every few years, they used to face different working environments to procure food and plan monthly menus.

Figure 3. School meal procurement after launching the public meal center (Source: Authors work)

5.3. Creating PFP value chains – the role of judicial governance

The features of judicial governance characterize the concepts of monitoring, sanction, and incentive (See **Table 3**). In this context, two major themes emerged: Food safety and budget execution. In terms of food safety, the dietitians’ main concerns were food poisoning and pesticide residues. The results demonstrated that as the legal monitoring and penalty systems in food safety primarily rely on centralized, national assurance systems, there was rarely space for actors such as individual school kitchens to be involved in the policy discussion and

decision-making process. In addition, budget execution (reporting) is one of the administrative burdens on a school canteen.

The noticeable aspect is the monitoring system for local food use. The public meal center established the channel to guarantee the assurance of locally grown agri-food products. Kitchens used to record their quantities and items used by collecting the organic labels of each material, as the national organic certificate exists, and schools have an obligation to keep records for budget subsidies. However, given the fragmented market environments and that there is no certification in Korea for locally grown food, in practice, the monitoring of the quantity and kinds of locally sourced food consumed at school canteens was impeded. On the side of previous supply conditions, small private distributors cannot afford to check and record the regional origins of food due to the complicated involvement of middlemen in the chain and the lack of an institutional system of tracing. P1 asserted that

One of the advantages of local food is that we know each other. When we handed our products over to middlemen, we didn't know who would eat our products. But at least for the school canteens in our regions, we can trace the route of our products. **P1 Head of public meal center of Gunsan, Farmer**

Moreover, the distinct merits of the local food in Jeonbuk are freshness, safety, and faith in the locality (Choi and Kim, 2015). Considering the circumstance of the existing fresh vegetable agri-food distribution and PFP administration, explicitly requiring and stipulating the degree of “freshness” in the bidding process is doubtful. The locality matter is similar. The current national laws relevant to public procurement and the origin labels on agricultural products do not allow the labeling of local origins. However, along with the legitimacy of the public channel, the public center institutions assured these features, and farmers and dietitians can utilize the system to control freshness, safety, and locality.

The centers have made it easier to verify the local food use because they can afford to manage quantities and product items from each farm directly, consumption by school canteens, and their time series through their own online system and direct relations with farmers. This allows us to study the stock and flow of local products in the region without reporting from the school side. Based on this change, Provincial Government agreed with Education Office that the outcome of each region would be announced on the official website to facilitate the movement towards local food use by schools and citizens. In addition, the comprehensive monitoring systems used by meal centers partially replaced the food safety function, as centers have adopted the national food safety certification of the agri-food chain following the Jeonbuk Provincial Government guidelines.

One of the challenges in the legal area that we found was the budget burden. Setting up the conditions to source locally grown food from small farms to public kitchens required the financial resources to build physical storage and distribution facilities and to employ human resources. Consequently, all of the interviewees indicated that it was necessary to secure a high level of public involvement and support to develop a public meal center and the relevant governance in this agri-food ecosystem. One of the workshop participants explained that

We recognized that these public meal centers are relatively unique and useful for the local circular economy. On the one hand, we have to accept the fact that building the center and designing the guarantee system requires extensive public investment. I hope the central government establishes a secure and comprehensive budget for public meal programs. **Workshop participant**

Table 3. Institutional changes to the Jeonbuk Province school meal program (Source: Authors work)

	Previous PFP institutions	Changed institutions for local food use
Legislative governance	(Guideline) school kitchens follow the fixed, quantitative standards in the Education Office guideline	-PG's involvement in the guideline -Introduction of locally processed food
	(Contract) online bids based on MEAT (Most Economically Advantageous Tender)	-Free contract with the center available to set up a joint agreement for the use of local food through the center
	(Policy structure) Fragmented programs design and implementation -Three different programs with two heterogeneous departments in charge	Integrated programs and tasks -Planned cultivation -Integrated masterplan with local food and school meals by the municipality
Executive governance	(Knowledge sharing) -Bidding systems, daily discussion Individual, informal kitchen–distributor communication No farmer–kitchen channel -No place to discuss details and standards directly in advance -A committee mainly composed of the education side; a deliberative body held twice annually	-Farmers–schools communicative channel set up by the center and committee -Public meal center committee established and enhanced -An additional monthly working group committee with the public meal center
	(Service implementation) Rare participation in PFP Lack of technical response to consumer needs regarding quality and logistics; concerns about price and sales uncertainties	-Municipalities establish and support the public meal center -(Farmers) The center and its relevant policies assist farmers to meet standards and expectations (e.g., collective training, annual cultivation plan, price determination) -(Kitchens) The center assures the value of local food to guarantee freshness and locality, and it reduces the knowledge gap
Judicial governance	(Monitoring) School's obligation to report on organic use but not local food use	Same as previously

	(Inspection & Audit) Food safety by the national agency, budget settlement	(New) Local food use monitoring through the center with conditional support
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6. Conclusions and Implications

6.1. Conclusions

This paper reviewed and applied a conceptual framework aimed at identifying the role of PFP institutions in value chain governance by studying a case study of a South Korean local school meal program. The analytical framework of this study came from combining the framework and literature on SOI and value chains to provide three dimensions: legislative, executive, and judicial governance. The findings demonstrate how each stakeholder responds to the new school meal program. The analysis of the dialogue of the actors reveals the list and links of the relevant institutions of PFP. In turn, we demonstrate how institutions pursue the objective of procuring local food. It means that the changing roles and concerns of municipalities across the realm of school meal procurement have invigorated the relevant institutions surrounding the public meal center, which has resulted in the municipality having transformed itself from PFP “rule-follower” to a “rule-setter.”

The findings also present the public meal center as a platform that has orchestrated the knowledge exchange processes and integration of farmers and kitchens into the school meal value chain. The relevant committee and everyday dialogue enabled farmers and kitchens to share the knowledge and value of locally grown food. These PFP institutions and the relevant activities of actors contributed to creating a new regional agri-food ecosystem. Accordingly, all of the actors, including local ecopreneur farms, actively joined the series of value chain governance with a high level of expectation that demonstrated their active embrace of SOI. Through the analysis of legislative and executive governance of the value chain, it became evident that the public characteristics of the center significantly enhance the active communication and participation of school kitchens and producers in the chain. The relevant

national law, municipal ordinances, and public policies officially assure the public status of the meal center. In particular, the results of executive governance indicate that the meal center contributed to addressing the constraints that underlie the food selection criteria and quality assurance through its committee activities and daily communication. A public meal center facilitated the transformation of arms-length relations between kitchens and distributors into in-house partnerships with farmers. Our study further extends the agricultural cooperatives literature and contributes to a better understanding of the role of a municipality and an agri-food intermediary in the governance process involving producers and kitchens (Lee et al., 2020, Ma et al., 2022, Ma et al., 2023). Considering to the institutional context on PFP, still more research is needed to fully uncover different roles and governance structures in agrifood ecosystems. Thus, our research further encourages to study how existing agricultural cooperatives could transform into agricultural ecosystems through SOI.

6.2. Implications

The further implications for PFP policymakers and practitioners are associated with the policy environments in our case. This case might suggest the potential necessity of the publicly run meal center as well as the need for prudent consideration in diverse conditions of PFP. As examined in the findings section, PFP in the regional agri-food ecosystem may be vulnerable to external impacts and weaknesses regarding service performance. Each stakeholder in the case seem to have less resistance to public intervention, which might cause the public meal center to work properly in Korea. Through previous lengthy discussions and efforts in civil society, South Korea has universal free lunches at schools equipped with their own kitchens, supported by municipal budgets that led to an agreement that government involvement in PFP could be justified. The certain level of consensus regarding public intervention in PFP and agri-food systems in Korea may differ from other societies, such as the EU member states.

From the perspective of the ongoing debates on urban sustainable agri-food systems, further research is needed to redefine the role of the agri-food intermediate entity in PFP comparing its functions to those of other similar models, such as the “food hub” in agri-food ecosystems. Policymakers may need to review and discuss which rural and urban environments are suitable for the public meal center as an orchestrator and its economic and social impacts. In addition, as this paper focused on the institutional dynamics of SOI, rather than its impacts, it may need to be complemented by the quantitative evaluation of the impacts of SOI. Given the limited range of resources and objects of this research, as the notions of government and market systems vary by country, our study may be supplemented by further case studies and implementation cases in other rapidly growing developing countries.

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Appendix A: The data source of documents and regulations (Source: Authors work)

Title	The authorities	Year
School meal guidelines of Jeonbuk Province	Jeonbuk Education Office	2018
Local food and school meal strategy of Jeonbuk Province	Jeonbuk Provincial Government	2017
Handout – Conference on Local Food Plan Policy	Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs	2018
Act on origin labeling of agricultural and fishery product	Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs	2018
Act on the revitalization of direct trade in agricultural products	Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs	2015
Wanju local food strategy	Wanju municipality	2013
School Meals Act	Ministry of Education	2020
The guidelines for school meal center	Ministry of Education	2014
Jeonbuk provincial ordinance of school meal	Jeonbuk Provincial Government	2015
Wanju municipal ordinance of local food and PFP	Wanju Municipality	2020
Gunsan municipal ordinance of local food and PFP	Gunsan Municipality	2018
Gunsan municipal ordinance of school meal	Gunsan Municipality	2017